

Methodology for Workflow Readiness for NAIRR Pilot Resources

Karan Vahi¹, Mats Rynge¹, Rajiv Mayani¹ and Ewa Deelman¹

USC Information Sciences Institute

Draft: V1

Date: April 6th, 2026

1. Introduction	1
2. AI Workloads	2
2.1 Preparation of data to a form suitable for training an AI model	2
2.2 Training an AI model	3
2.3 Evaluating the model	3
2.4 Inference	4
2.5 Post Processing, Fine Tuning, or Refining the Output of the Model	4
3. Methodology for Assessing Resource Workflow Readiness	5
3.1 Suitable Workloads	5
3.2 Data Movement	5
3.3 Remote Orchestration / Submission of jobs / Distributed Computing	6
3.4 Container Technologies Support	6
3.5 Support for AI Frameworks and Models	7
3.6 Specialized Hardware / GPUs	7
3.7 Pegasus Readiness	7
3.7.1 Distributed Computing	7
3.7.2 Resource Co-location	8
3.7.3 API Calls in Workflow Tasks	8
3.8 Readiness Testing Harness	8
3.8.1 Snapshots	10

1. Introduction

NSF-led NAIRR Pilot provides scientists the opportunity to leverage about 30 different resources for their science. The resources offered are heterogeneous ranging from traditional HPC-based large computing resources to cloud-based and/or kubernetes-managed resources. Some of these resources are general-purpose resources that can be used for executing non-AI workloads such as large simulations, data processing, while others are tailored for AI workloads. AI workloads themselves can be characterized as a combination of the following steps depending on a scientist's particular use case:

- Preparation of data in a form suitable for AI model training
- Training an AI model, including augmenting large language models with additional data that it was not trained on to provide better answers/responses.
- Evaluating the model
- Doing inference against a trained model, whereby new unseen data is fed to the model to make predictions or conclusions.
- Post-processing, fine-tuning or refining the output of the model

For the past twenty years, scientific workflow management systems, such as Pegasus, have provided the necessary automation of computation execution across heterogeneous systems. Such technologies are also needed in the context of the NAIRR Pilot to enable scientists to productively use the available compute and data storage resources. It is no longer reasonable for scientists to log onto individual resources, pull the needed data, perform the computations, and then offload the results to the next resource. Even if scientists use scripts to automate these operations, this type of automation is cumbersome. The scripts are brittle, error-prone, and unable to keep up with changing resource characteristics and availability. At the same time, since AI workflows require different types of resources for the various workflow stages, there is a need to submit jobs, invoke data operations, and transfers from a user-facing location that is separate from the user-side services and the capabilities provided by the resources. Thus, the most viable solution for effectively leveraging the NAIRR Pilot resources while maintaining productivity is to use a workflow management system.

To enable workflow management systems to perform the necessary orchestration, there is a need for secure APIs for resource provisioning, job submission, data storage, and data transfers. Keeping in mind the wide range of diverse resources offered as part of the NAIRR pilot, we recognize that it is infeasible for any workflow system to support all these resources natively. Instead, this proposed methodology is meant to be a starting point for CI practitioners, workflow developers, and providers to develop workflow automation solutions for AI applications on these resources.

2. AI Workloads

AI workloads are becoming pervasive across various domains and vary widely in their resource requirements. At a high level, they can be characterized as follows.

2.1 Preparation of data to a form suitable for training an AI model

An often overlooked but important part of model training is having good and clean datasets for the models to train on. As part of this process, users may have to extract data from various sources, harmonize them, and label them accordingly. This process can often be done on CPU resources. With NAIRR Pilot, users have access to numerous traditional HPC resources that, in

addition to having GPUs available, have a lot of CPUs accessible for the users. NAIRR-Pilot high-throughput resources also offer significant CPU cycles.

2.2 Training an AI model

This is the most resource-intensive phase of an AI pipeline, where users train models on their datasets and refine them over time. Model training is often an iterative process, where each pass over the data leads to further improvements in model accuracy. This stage is commonly referred to as the machine learning phase and can involve either supervised or unsupervised learning. Model training often requires access to GPUs and specialized hardware such as TPUs.

Deep learning is a type of model training that uses neural networks, where the training process adjusts the weights across multiple network layers. This approach typically requires access to large numbers of GPUs or other specialized hardware, which can be accessed through NAIRR Pilot.

Federated machine learning is a technique where multiple “local” nodes collaboratively train a shared model on their own datasets. Instead of sending raw data to a central server, each node trains locally and periodically sends only model updates (such as weights or gradients) to a central aggregator. The aggregator combines these updates to form a global model, which is then redistributed back to the local nodes for further training.

Generative AI refers to models that can create new content such as text, images, or other media. Large Language Models (LLMs) are a common example, trained on vast datasets to generate human-like text. Similar generative techniques, such as diffusion models can also produce images and videos. Training an LLM is highly resource-intensive, and only a few NAIRR Pilot providers offer the capacity to support such work. However, many pre-trained models are now available through NAIRR Pilot providers. Training an LLM from scratch is a specialized and costly task, and most users are more likely to fine-tune or adapt existing models rather than build new ones from the ground up.

2.3 Evaluating the model

Once a model has been trained, it is important to evaluate its performance to ensure it meets the goals of the project. For machine learning models, this typically involves testing the model on data that was not used during training and measuring how accurately it produces the expected results. The evaluation should confirm that the model works well not only on the training data but also on new, unseen data.

For generative AI models, evaluation often includes reviewing outputs for quality, relevance, and consistency. In many cases, human judgment is needed to assess whether the generated text, images, or other content are appropriate and useful for the intended application. For both ML and

generative AI models, the evaluation should also verify that the model produces reliable results across a variety of inputs and does not show unwanted biases.

2.4 Inference

Inference is the process of using a trained machine learning model or an LLM to generate outputs or predictions on new data that the model has not seen before. This is the stage where the model is put into practical use, applying what it learned during training to solve real-world problems. Inference can run on a variety of resources, including CPUs, GPUs, and specialized inference hardware, all of which are available through the NAIRR Pilot. NAIRR Pilot also provides access to commercial providers that offer highly optimized infrastructure for fast and efficient inference.

In traditional machine learning, inference might involve using a trained model to classify images, detect anomalies in network traffic, or predict equipment failures based on sensor readings. For generative AI, inference can be used to produce text, images, audio, or video from prompts or input data. Examples include generating synthetic medical images for research, producing high-quality translations in real time, or creating visual assets for scientific visualization.

A common application of generative AI is deploying a chatbot that interacts with users through an LLM. For example, a research support chatbot could answer questions about datasets or assist with documentation searches by generating accurate, context-aware responses. Another growing area is AI agents, which use models such as LLMs to plan and execute sequences of actions toward a goal. AI agents can combine inference with tools, APIs, or other data sources to perform complex tasks autonomously. For instance, a research-focused AI agent might gather information from multiple datasets, run computations, and summarize results in a format ready for publication.

2.5 Post Processing, Fine Tuning, or Refining the Output of the Model

Once a model produces its initial output, there are often additional steps that can improve its usefulness, accuracy, or alignment with the desired outcome. Post-processing can include cleaning or formatting the results, filtering out unwanted content, or combining outputs from multiple models to produce a more reliable answer. In traditional machine learning, this might involve applying thresholding to classification scores, smoothing time series predictions, or merging results from an ensemble of models. For generative AI, post-processing could include re-ranking generated text, enhancing image resolution, or applying content moderation filters.

Fine-tuning is the process of refining an existing model and adapting it to perform better on a specific dataset or task. This can be especially effective for LLMs, where training from scratch is impractical. Fine-tuning allows the model to retain its general capabilities while learning to perform well in a specific domain, such as legal text analysis, biomedical research, or climate modeling.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is an increasingly popular method for refining the responses of LLMs by adding relevant context from external knowledge sources. In a RAG

workflow, the model first retrieves relevant documents, database entries, or other structured information, then uses this context to generate a more accurate and complete response. This approach can greatly improve factual accuracy and domain specificity. RAG workloads can be efficiently run on GPUs and are well supported by many NAIRR Pilot resources. Common use cases include scientific literature review, question answering over institutional data, and interactive research assistants.

3. Methodology for Assessing Resource Workflow Readiness

We ground our work in the expertise gained while developing Pegasus WMS over the past 20 years, and evolving the system as the target CI changed, such as changes in high-performance computing systems, the advent of computational clouds, and now edge resources. This methodology attempts to identify high-level capabilities that are required for a resource to enable workflow execution and specifically AI workflows. For each high-level capability, we created a list of sub-capabilities that, if existent, can be deemed to be supporting that requirement.

3.1 Suitable Workloads

As part of this methodology, we also aim to document what type of AI workloads a particular resource is suited for. This is mainly derived from researching the documentation and online training materials for the resources. The aim of this is to provide a quick overview of what type of AI workflows a resource is suited for.

We first identify the important functionalities/capabilities needed to support automated workflow execution.

3.2 Data Movement

This capability refers to the resource providing a way to stage in datasets and also stage out any outputs as required. Even if the workflow is orchestrated within a single resource, staging data is an essential component of orchestration, which allows data integration and result publication. This capability can be achieved by any one of the following sub-capabilities:

- Web-based data management
- Object Stores, such as Amazon's S3
- Globus Online Endpoint
- SCP
- HTTP

3.3 Remote Orchestration / Submission of jobs / Distributed Computing

This capability enables a resource to support the submission of jobs from a remote endpoint and/or allows jobs to be run on a resource while connecting back to a central coordination point. In the context of scientific workflows, this largely revolves around the following sub-capabilities:

- SSH connectivity: ability to connect over SSH to an entry point of the resource, from where a job can be submitted to the resource.
- API for submitting jobs.
- Ability to launch pilot jobs. Pilot jobs are a commonly deployed mechanism whereby a user submits jobs to a resource provider to provision resources for a user's application tasks. Pilot jobs prove especially beneficial when the resource is oversubscribed i.e. the jobs in the queue waiting to run are asking for more resources than what the resource provider can fulfill. Another scenario, where deployment of pilot jobs is beneficial when a user's workload has a lot of short-running tasks, and one does not want to incur scheduling delays for each task. This technique allows users to acquire a small subset of resources, and then overlay a resource manager on top of them to run their application tasks efficiently.
- Outbound network connectivity from the resource Outbound network connectivity is important when the workflow system is deployed externally to the resource. This allows the pilot jobs to connect back to the resource provisioner setup.

3.4 Container Technologies Support

Application containers such as Docker and Apptainer/Singularity provide a way to package complex software and its dependencies. The sub capabilities that apply here are:

- Support for Docker
- Support for Apptainer

Use of containers enables providers to supply well-defined supported environments for running popular AI models to the users. Containers enable packaging an AI model with all its necessary components—such as code, dependencies, libraries, and configurations—into a single, portable unit. They also enable users to version control their environment along with the code base, allowing for tracking the environment in which a particular model was trained. Use of containers also provides natural isolation between users and minimizes vulnerabilities for a specific user's software stack/deployment, affecting other users.

Some providers may require the models to be registered in a container registry/hub before they can be deployed by the users on the resource infrastructure.

3.5 Support for AI Frameworks and Models

This capability indicates whether the resource can run commonly used AI frameworks and is prepared to support training or inference with large-scale models. Sub-capabilities include:

Framework Support: Availability of widely used AI frameworks (e.g., PyTorch, TensorFlow).

Large-Scale / Foundation Models: Ability to deploy, fine-tune, or serve large language models and other foundation models.

3.6 Specialized Hardware / GPUs

AI applications are optimized for and make heavy use of GPU resources. While this capability is generally available on a NAIRR resource, it is listed here for the general purpose of categorizing a resource as ready for AI workflows.

The sub capabilities that apply here are:

- Multi GPU nodes
- Multi node (ability to use GPUs across multiple nodes to do distributed deep learning)

3.7 Pegasus Readiness

Although there are a number of different workflow management systems (WMSs), here we explore the resource readiness in terms of Pegasus workflows, as the WMS allows for orchestration of computations and data movement across distributed resources, for example from the edge to the cloud. Evaluating a resource's readiness for AI workflows in the context of Pegasus WMS begins with determining where Pegasus should be deployed to take the best advantage of the resource's interfaces and capabilities.

3.7.1 Distributed Computing

In some cases, Pegasus is installed in a distributed computing configuration, with the deployment being anywhere on the network. From there it can orchestrate tasks on remote systems using APIs, pilot jobs, or direct SSH submissions. This approach allows jobs to be sent from an external workflow submit node, such as the ACCESS Pegasus endpoint, to a NAIRR Pilot resource without requiring Pegasus to be installed locally.

3.7.2 Resource Co-location

In other situations, Pegasus is deployed directly on the resource itself. This co-located approach often means it is directly integrated with the job scheduler and shared filesystem. It is most

common when policies or security requirements make external job submission infeasible, as workflows can then be launched entirely within the resource's internal environment.

3.7.3 API Calls in Workflow Tasks

Some resources do not directly support Pegasus-style execution. They may lack SSH access, batch submission interfaces, or pilot job capabilities. In these cases, readiness evaluation focuses on whether a resource can still support workflow orchestration. While these systems are not directly schedulable through HTCondor or SLURM, they can still be used in Pegasus workflows, if the jobs in the workflow directly interface with the resource using its provided APIs. For example, Pegasus might store intermediate data in S3, trigger a model endpoint for training, or insert an inference step using a script such as `call_model.py`, with results stored locally or in S3 for downstream processing.

3.8 Readiness Testing Harness

This work includes a Workflow Readiness Testing Harness, which will be used to assess whether a compute or data resource is prepared for workflow execution by Pegasus WMS. This type of testing goes beyond verifying that workflows run correctly. It also evaluates the infrastructure for compatibility, automation capability, and operational robustness under realistic conditions. Because of the differences in resource types and capabilities, the harness will use slightly different methodologies for the different resources. Some of the planned tests:

- Simple PyTorch based training
- Simple PyTorch based inference
- Ollama LLM, container based job with included LLM

Taking into account the above criteria we have catalogued the following NAIRR resources along these capabilities. These are representative of the type of resources available as part of the NAIRR Pilot.

- AWS SAGEMaker / Bedrock
- Samba Nova
- HuggingFace Spaces
- NVIDIA DGX Cluster
- GROQ Cloud
- PATH
- Jetstream 2 GPU
- NCSA Delta AI
- PSC Bridges2
- Neocortex
- Purdue Anvil

- SDSC (Voyager)
- TACC VISTA

Below we include snapshots of the current version of the mockup document. For editing/updating the content please edit the google sheet [NAIRR Workflow Readiness: V1](#).

3.8.1 Snapshots

NAIRR Workflow Readiness: V1 Set 1

	AWS SAGEMaker / Bedrock	Samba Nova	HuggingFace Spaces	NVIDIA DGX Cluster	GROQ Cloud	PATH
Type of Resource	Web + API	API	Web	Batch / K8s / API	API	Batch
Suitable Workloads						
Data Cleaning and Preparation	Y		Y	Y		Y
Training: Machine Learning	Y		Y	Y	N	Y
Training: Generative AI	Y	N	N	Y	N	N
Inference: Machine Learning	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Inference: Generative AI	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Resource Description Link						
Notes	Model Training, Preprocessing and Post Processing, Inference jobs	RAG, fast inference	ML models, transformers? inference https://huggingface.co/blog/naxson/make-your-own-rag https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/main/en/preprocessing	Build foundation models, fine tune them, provides serverless inference	mainly inference against supported LLM models, developing agentic tools, text to speech, speech to text, interpreting images etc, RAG example against presidential speeches, NO Training.	Training, inference, RAG
Data Movement/Storage						
Web Upload (for more platform style solutions like the industry ones)	Y (through Studio interface)	Y	Y		maybe via playground	
Object Store	Y	N	Y			Y (OSDF)
Globus Online	N	N				
SCP	Possible			Y (scp, ftp, rsync)		
Notes			datasets are available on hugging face hub and can be loaded with a single line of code		encoding images/ audio in base 64encoding and passing it to the Groq API	in built htcondor file transfer mechanisms
Remote Orchestration / Submission of jobs / Distributed Computing						
SSH connectivity	Y			Y (can ssh to headnode)		
API for submitting jobs	Y	Y? (OpenAI API only against the LLM)	Y (But for setting up an inference endpoint), also run inference	N	Y (asynchronous batch rest api and they have a python library for it too)	
Glideins / Pilot Jobs	N	N		N		Y
Outbound connectivity	Y	N	N/A	?		Y
Container Technologies Support						
Docker	Y	N	Y	Y (using enroot)		
Apptainer	N	Y				Y
Do containers need to be vetted? or put in some particular repository where they can be pulled from?			(from DockerHUB, ECR, GCR and Azure ACR)	N (however need to be run via enroot)		
Ability to launch Common AI Tools (Already deployed)						
PyTorch	Y	Y (conversion to Samba Flow required)	Y	Y	Y (with conversion using GroqFlow)	Y
LLM / Foundation Models	Y (various available), need to grant access in the console	Y (various available)	Y	Y (ALMA model)		
Specialized Hardware / GPUs						
Multi GPU	Y		Y	Y	N	Y
GPU Capabilities		state-of-the-art AI chip, the SN40L.				custom inference chip
Pegasus Readiness (Remote)						
Preferred Pegasus Deployment	Possible	N/A	Possible		Possible	
Launch Pilots			Distributed Computing + API in user jobs	Maybe		
API for submitting jobs	Y (requires development), one could launch processing jobs for pre and post processing, also API for launching training jobs exists				Y (requires development)	N
Pegasus Readiness (Local)						
workflow submit nodes that allow users to install wms with access to local scheduler	N/A	N/A	N/A	Possible	N/A (provides only API endpoints)	
access to resource shared filesystems?				Maybe		
				Y		

NAIRR Workflow Readiness: V1 Set 2

	Jetstream 2 GPU	NCSA Delta AI	PSC Bridges2	Neocortex	Purdue Anvil	SDSC (Voyager)	TACC VISTA (Should we club all TACC NAIR Pilot resources together?)
Type of Resource	Cloud	Batch	Batch	Batch	Batch	K8s	
Suitable Workloads							
Data Cleaning and Preparation	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Training: Machine Learning	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Training: Generative AI	N	N	N	?	N	N	N
Inference: Machine Learning	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Inference: Generative AI	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	
Resource Description Link							
Notes	training, inference, RAG, service deployments	training, inference, RAG	training, inference, performing model finetuning/inference with models such as Llama-2 7B and Llama-3 8B, RAG	foundation and large language models such as BERT, GPT-J, and Transformer, or combine supported TensorFlow or PyTorch layers	AI model training and inference, RAG	training, inference, develop their own deep learning models using developer tools and libraries from Habana Labs. LLM	training.
Data Movement/Storage							
Web Upload (for more platform style solutions like the industry ones)	N			N	Y	N	
Object Store	Y			N	N	N	
Globus Online	Y (as personal connect option)	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y
SCP	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	?	Y
Notes		rsync for small datasets against login node	sftp, rsync	rsync, sftp	rsync, scp, sftp		
Remote Orchestration / Submission of jobs / Distributed Computing							
SSH connectivity	N/A	Y (but with 2 factor)	Y (but with 2 factor)	Y	Y	Y	Y (but with 2 factor)
API for submitting jobs	Y (Open Stack?)	N	N	N	N	Y	N
Glideins / Pilot Jobs	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y (if outbound connectivity is possible)	Y (possible)
Outbound connectivity	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y (should be possible via k8s when launching pods)	Y (assuming outbound connectivity as frontera)
Container Technologies Support							
Docker	Y				Y (on anvil cloud)	Y	
Aptainer	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	?	Y (on frontera, by extension should be on vista but not sure)
Do containers need to be vetted? or put in some particular repository where they can be pulled from?	N				harbor registry in anvil cloud for docker containers	via Local GitLab	
Ability to launch Common AI Tools (Already deployed)							
PyTorch	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
LLM / Foundation Models	Y (LLM service)		Y			Y (via vLLM fork)	
Specialized Hardware / GPUs							
Multi GPU	Y	Y	Y	Y (custom chip)	Y	Y	Y
GPU Capabilities							
Pegasus Readiness (Remote)							
Preferred Pegasus Deployment	Distributed Computing + Pilot Jobs		Resource Colocated, Distributed Computing				
Launch Pilots	Y	Y	Y	Y?	Y	Possible (k8 based, if outbound connectivity is allowed)	Y (assuming outbound connectivity)
API for submitting jobs	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Pegasus Readiness (Local)							
workflow submit nodes that allow users to install wms with access to local scheduler		N (can install and run condor in user space if the admins were to agree)					
access to resource shared filesystems?		Y					